

ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE OF ANTIMICROBIAL PAINTS ENHANCED WITH BIOCIDES SMART RELEASE TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract

The growing demand for surface protection technologies that meet the requirements of material durability and environmental sustainability has led to the introduction of antimicrobial paints in the market. These coatings integrate a passive and uncontrolled release of biocides and fungicides, resulting in biocidal functionality between for a time period between a half and two years. The limited bio-resistance of the materials allows the growth of micro-organisms, which negatively affect health, leading to hypersensitivity and allergic reactions such as rhinitis and asthma. In this study, the environmental impacts associated with the manufacturing and the use of enhanced antimicrobial outdoor coating materials were investigated, using a Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) methodology, based on the ISO 14040 standard. A comparative analysis was carried out between conventional paints and antimicrobial paints adapting smart release mechanisms of eco-acceptable biocide affecting coating durability and prolonging service-life. The integration of a smart biocide release mechanism in surface coatings results to significant environmental benefits by prolonging the materials' bio-protection and improving human health and quality of life.

Keywords: *Anti-fungal paint, Biocide control release; Comparative Analysis; Environmental Impact Assessment; Life Cycle Assessment*

1. Introduction

Weathering and deterioration of building materials can occur due to the growth of microorganisms, such as algae, fungi, etc. The determining factors which influence the growth of mold on building materials have proven to be moisture as well as temperature and time (1). Therefore, the development of new durable coating materials proper for application in humid condition is necessary. Bio-resistancy of building and finishing materials usually requires addition of dedicated bioactive chemicals, so-called biocides. These chemicals offer protection by providing antimicrobial action, hence reducing the

micro-organisms population, but also negatively affecting the durability of material, i.e. induce biodegradation. In addition, biocides are also used to prevent the growth of micro-organisms (algae, fungi and bacteria) that create unhealthy indoor environmental conditions or affect the aesthetic value. Traditionally, the action of biocides in materials, (e.g. coatings, plasters) is based on a passive and uncontrolled release principle, i.e. molecular dispersion of the active ingredients in the material matrix. As a consequence these bio-active agents have a high and inherent mobility in the matrix, which causes an initial boost in biocide activity and a steep decrease when time proceeds.(2) Consequently, coatings in a built environment usually exhibit biocidal functionality between 0.5 and 2 years, whereas the desired service life in building practice is at least 10 years. Application of an increased biocide concentration only results in a minor prolongation of the material service-life. Besides the environmental impact of early replacement of such functional coatings, an inherent disadvantage of the inefficiency of the traditional release method is the emission of a relatively large amount of biocide molecules into the environment. In addition, the limited bio-resistance of the material will allow the growth of micro-organisms, which negatively affect health, leading to hypersensitivity and allergic reactions such as rhinitis and asthma. This is a prevalent problem in homes and occupational buildings worldwide (3, 4). Moreover, growing ecological demands and international environmental legislation increase even more the pressure on the materials' performance. First, the application of active agents for materials' bioresistance is regulated by the Biocidal Product Directive 98/08/EC, which sets strict conditions with respect to the use of bio-active agents (5). And second, the industrial trend towards eco-friendlier building products is often accompanied with an increase in the biodegradability, requiring even more biocides to compensate. In order the paint industry to provide a prediction on the environmental impact of controlled release technology, a life cycle analysis was performed, comparing different conventional and antimicrobial coating products. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology is a suitable and valuable tool to assess the environmental impact of materials, products and services during their life cycle and it should be part of the decision-making process towards sustainability (6).

The objectives of this paper is to examine the environmental performance of conventional and biocide containing materials. Several case studies have been developed in order to evaluate the finishing materials, which implement a "smart" release mechanism consisting of an induced response on external stimuli in finishing materials, and have an extended service-life. The selected smart release mechanism is based on functionalized mineral (nano-clay) particles, which reduce the amount of biocides required considerably (at least a factor of 5 compared to ordinary materials) and tune the release systems to "environmental friendlier" biocides. As a result, the life cycle analysis of the different antimicrobial paint model systems investigated allows the evaluation of their sustainability in relation with the achievable environmental benefits, as a measure of ecological quality, based on our knowledge of the influence on the environment.

2. Goal and Scope definition

2.1 Goal definition

The *goal of the present LCA study* is to determine the environmental footprint associated with the production and use of antimicrobial paint, to compare conventional antimicrobial paints in comparison with paints adopting smart release mechanisms of eco-acceptable biocide and finally to evaluate the effect of coating durability and prolong service-life.

2.2 Scope definition

2.2.1 System definition, calculation and functional unit

In the studied case, the system is the set of processes that constitute the production, the transportation between the factory and the residence and the application of the coating material. This system includes different subsystems such as the individual activities of gathering raw materials or the process for the production of the paint. The selected calculation unit is one kg of coating produced in the factory, equal to the paint needed to cover 10 m² wall surface which is considered as the functional unit of the system.

2.2.2 System boundaries

The system includes the stages from the extraction of raw materials needed for the production to the application of the antimicrobial paint. Secondary processes have not been considered due to the fact that their environmental loads represent a small percentage of the total load associated to the product under study. However, the impacts associated with the energy production have been considered.

2.2.3 Selected impact categories, Impact assessment and methodology

The Impact Assessment methodology used in this LCA study is the Impact 2002+. According to this methodology, the Impact Categories which are being taken into consideration are allocated to four Damage Categories: Human Health, Ecosystem Quality, Climate Change and Resources. In Figure 1 the Impact Categories related to each Damage Category are presented.

Fig. 1: Impact 2000+ Impact categories.

2.2.4 Assumptions

For the studied cases of antimicrobial paint the following assumptions have been made:

- Water based paint was selected for this study

-The reference antimicrobial paint is considered to contain 2000 ppm biocide per 1kg of paint (0.2% w/w) and this product is estimated to have a lifespan of 5 years.

-The antimicrobial agent used, is considered to be a non-VOC broad spectrum, highly effective antimicrobial agent hence their emissions in the production phase of the antimicrobial paint were considered negligible.

-In order to achieve the desired controlled release of the biocide, nanoclay particles were considered as an encapsulant. The diffusion rate of the antimicrobial agent is depended on its encapsulation. Therefore, paint with no biocide encapsulation is assumed to release the whole amount of the biocide within the products life span. On the other hand, the slow release rate provided by the nano-clay is assumed to reduce the amount of biocide released up to 70% within the life cycle of paint (7, 8).

- Humidity and rainfall were considered to transfer the biocide to the aquifer, while an amount of biocide is assumed to be retained by the soil.
- External walls of the building are considered to be on humid conditions several days a year, therefore are more susceptible to mold growth.
- A typical lifespan of a building is considered to be 60 years.
- The packaging of the paint (PP pot) was taken into consideration in the use phase.

3. Life cycle inventory analysis

A product's life cycle assessment is a framework that can be used to identify inputs, outputs and impacts within the life time of a product. In this stage, all data which are either entering the system (like raw materials, water and other natural inputs) or coming out to the environment (like products, air emissions, by-products and wastes) are recorded and quantified, based on mass balances. Therefore, the inventory includes the following steps: a) development of the alternative paint and application case studies and mapping of the inputs and outputs in each process and case as a whole; b) collection of the data required for the calculation from the data inventory and c) development of an appropriate mass calculation model based on the assumptions made and the data collected. The life cycle of antimicrobial paint is pictured in Figure 2.

In this study different formulations of antimicrobial paint have been evaluated by taking into consideration their application, their life span and their environmental impact. Therefore, a comparative analysis was carried out between conventional paints and antimicrobial paints adopting smart release mechanisms. In Table 1 the alternative case studies for conventional and antimicrobial paint are presented and information about the presence of a control release mechanism as well as the life span of each product is given. An antimicrobial paint's use phase describes the application, the maintenance and the replacement that take place during its operational phase.

Fig. 2: Life cycle of paint enriched with biocide.

Table 1: Case studies of water based-paint.

Case study	Nanoclay concentration on paint (% w/w)	Biocide release factor (%)	Times of repainting	Product lifespan (years)
0	-	-	12	5
1	-	100	12	5
2	1	30	12	5
3	0,33	100% free on paint 30% reserved on nanoclay	12	5
4	1	30	4	15
5	0,33	100% free on paint 30% reserved on nanoclay	4	15

4. Impact assessment

In order to understand the environmental importance and to estimate the possible environmental impacts of antimicrobial paints adopting smart release mechanisms, the effects of the environmental burdens identified in the Inventory Analysis stage have been assessed. In this stage a connection between the recorded inputs and outputs and the environmental impact of such antimicrobial paint has been examined. A comparison between the studied products is made based on selected indicators. By comparing the impact between a conventional and an antimicrobial paint, estimation on the impact of the biocide leaching can be made. Table 2 presents the impact of conventional paint used for covering 10 m² of wall (CS 0). The results of the assessment are being shown as the accumulated contributions of paint application and the use and disposal to various environmental impact categories over the life time of the building. The case studies start with the application of the paint and as the time passes, every environmental impact corresponds to the specific time period, is added. A 60 year time phase is chosen because it is long enough to show the long-term consequences of paint choices, while being a realistic operation period for a typical external wall.

Table 2: *Impact of conventional paint*

Damage category (Pt)	CS 0
Human health	2,47E-03
Ecosystem quality	2,47E-04
Climate change	2,57E-03
Resources	4,32E-03
Total	9,61E-03

4.1 Comparison of conventional paint to antimicrobial paint

In the frameworks of this study passive mechanisms of slow-release of eco-acceptable biocides in order the service life of finishing materials to be substantially extended, are being examined. The slow release concept refers to slowing down the diffusion rate of the biocide. In order to achieve this, a modified nano-clay surface carrying the antimicrobial agent, has been used. The nano-clay technique is more sophisticated and aims to be built in a retarding step before the actual diffusion of the biocide to the surface. A rapid decrease of the biocide concentration due to fast leaching can then be avoided with the condition that at the same initial biocide concentration the release of biocide will remain longer above the lowest effective dose. Usually, the active compounds are bound in a poor permeable carrier system with a high specific surface area, such as porous systems or (nano-)clay systems. This comprises a big step forward compared to the use of regular, non encapsulated, biocide systems. The comparison between encapsulated or not biocide systems has made the following life cycle assessment in order to provide the necessary information for the impact resulting from the use of such products (Table 3).

Table 3: Impact assessment of antimicrobial paint free and control release.

Damage category (Pt)	CS 1	CS 2	CS 3	%Improvement*
Human health	2,43E-03	2,41E-03	2,43E-03	0,70%
Ecosystem quality	1,98E-02	6,10E-03	1,53E-02	69,15%
Climate change	2,51E-03	2,49E-03	2,50E-03	0,84%
Resources	4,28E-03	4,25E-03	4,27E-03	0,87%
Total	2,90E-02	1,52E-02	2,45E-02	47,42%

By comparing CS 0 to CS 1, the amount of biocide leached to the environment affects mainly the Aquatic and Terrestrial ecotoxicity and therefore the ecosystem quality. By comparing CS 1 of free release with CS 2 of control release an improvement up to 69% in ecosystem quality is observed due to the reduced amount of biocide leached. When comparing the control release with a partially control release, the environmental impact is proportional to the total biocide leached. Free release is considered to be unpredictable. Encapsulation provides a potential environmentally acceptable and controlled mean, which prolongs biocidal activity in coatings (9, 10). According to literature, controlled release of certain biocides has resulted in a reduction in the threshold levels of biocides to prevent microbiological attack. Therefore slow or controlled diffusion of the active agents results to lower environmental impact.

4.2 Comparison of antimicrobial paints with different release rate and prolonged lifetime

In order to provide information on how the diffusion rate of the biocide through paint lifetime prolongation affects the environment, two alternative scenarios of CS 2 and CS 3 were devised. By reducing the release rate of the biocide to the environment by 1/3, it is assumed that the lifetime of the antimicrobial paint is significantly extended.. The lifespan of this paint is considered to be 15 years, reducing the times of repaint needed. The total amount of paint needed throughout the lifetime of the building is considered to be approximately 4.2 kg. The characterization values of these case studies in each impact category are shown in Table 4. All impacts were reduced thus resulting to more environmental friendly products even if the biocide is partial encapsulated.

Table 4: Impact assessment of controlled release antimicrobial paint with extended life time.

Damage category (Pt)	CS 4	CS 5
Human health	8,05E-04	8,08E-04
Ecosystem quality	2,03E-03	5,09E-03
Climate change	8,29E-04	8,34E-04
Resources	1,42E-03	1,42E-03
Total	5,08E-03	8,15E-03

Fig. 3: Total impact assessment per damage category using Impact 2002+.

4.3 Comparison of different release rates of the antimicrobial agent

The encapsulation of the biocide plays an important role on the release rate of the chemical agent to the environment. In order to evaluate the impact of alternative impregnation effectiveness of the materials different case studies of release rates were created. Each case study represents a different release rate and the overall impact in the main four damage categories is shown in figure 4. By controlling the biocide release the effects on ecosystem quality can be reduced dramatically. Therefore the production of new impregnation materials that can encapsulate the biocide and contribute to its slow release is essential. The reduction of the environmental impact by controlling the release rate of the biocide combined with increased paint durability is considered to be the key technology for the production of environmental friendly antimicrobial paints.

Fig. 4: Total impact assessment of different release rates of the biocide per damage category using Impact 2002+.

5. Conclusions

The LCA methodology can be a proper tool to achieve the study's objectives, which are the analysis, quantification and assessment of the environmental impact of various water based coatings. The overall environmental performances of conventional and antimicrobial paint have shown that the quantity of the biocide leached to the environment affects mainly the ecosystem quality and more specifically the aquatic and the terrestrial ecotoxicity category. In addition, the emissions compartment of the biocide plays an important role on its overall impact and solid wastes are considered to be the most detrimental. Antimicrobial paints adopting smart release mechanisms of eco-acceptable biocide are considered to have reduced diffusion rate, therefore affecting coating durability and prolonging its service-life. The integration of a smart biocide release mechanism in surface coatings results in significant environmental benefits. The impact of the biocide release can be reduced up to 3 times by prolonging the materials bio-protection and therefore minimizing the times of repaint. Free biocide release has presented the highest impact in all damage categories, while control release, resulting in an expanded lifespan of the paint, has shown less total impact than conventional paint.

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